

SYNTHESIS OF NIO THIN FILMS BY SPRAY PYROLYSIS METHOD AT DIFFERENT DEPOSITION TEMPERATURES AND TIMES

Rachida DJARALLAH ¹, Said BENRAMACHE ^{2,*}, Boubaker BENHAOUA ¹

¹Department of Physics, University of El-Oued, 39000, Algeria.

² Laboratoire des Matériaux, des Énergies et de l'Environnement, University of Biskra 07000, Algeria, s.benramache@univ-biskra.dz

ABSTRACT: Our objective is the preparation by the pyrolysis spray technique of thin layers of nickel oxide (NiO). Hexa-hydrated nickel denitrate [(NO₃)₂Ni, 6H₂O] was used as a precursor dissolved in ethanol of molar concentration, distance between beak and substrate and constant spraying rate of solution throughout the deposition process at 0.1M, 5 cm and 0.5 ml / min.. Then the study of the influence of substrate temperature and solution spray time on their structural, morphological and optical properties in order to determine their applicability in different fields. To obtain the latter, thin layers were developed on glass substrates heated firstly at different spraying times: 30 min, 1 hour, 1.5 hours and 2 hours with a constant temperature of 400 °C. Then changed the temperature from 350°C, 400°C, 450°C and 500°C with constant times of 1 hour. The structural analyzes (X-ray technique) show that all the samples have a cubic structure with a preferential orientation (200), is clear when the temperature is increased to 500°C especially when the temperature becomes 400°C and time of 60 min, that's why we chose the latter as the best result. Optical measurements have shown that the transmission it always remains higher at 70 %. Also, the increase in the volume of the sprayed solution leads to an increase in the size of the NiO crystallites from 28.67 nm to 38.67 nm for a temperature of 400°C which improves the homogeneity of the NiO film. At the same time, the optical interval is between 3.45 ev and 3.70 ev, these results are in agreement with the energy gap zone of NiO which is between 3.6 ev to 4 ev.

KEYWORDS: Thin films, Nickel Oxide, Spray pyrolysis, X-ray technique

1. INTRODUCTION

Transparent conducting oxides (TCO) are a unique class of materials which have the unusual ability to be both transparent (high visible optical transmission coefficient > 80%) and electrically conducting (low electrical resistivity <103 U.cm)[1-4]. Where higher performance is required, but which now includes work function, morphology, processing and structuring requirements, long-term stability, the lower cost and the abundance of ecological elements / materials.

As these needs began to emerge over the past five years, they have spurred a dramatic resurgence in field research, which has resulted in many new materials and processes. Thin transparent conductive oxide (TCO) films have received a lot of attention due to their wide applications in the opto-electronics industry. The most well-known TCOs such as In₂O₃: Sn (ITO), ZnO: Al (AZO) and SnO₂: F (FTO) are n-type semiconductors.

Although efforts have recently been devoted to the development of p-type TCOs such as delafossite CuMO₂ (M = Al, Cr, Ga, In, Sc, Y, B) [5-11], SrCu₂O₂ [12], oxysulfides of La CuOCh (Ch S, Se) [13,14] and binary oxides of NiO [15] and doped ZnO [16-19] and. al., their conductivities are always 3 to 4 orders of magnitude lower than those of n-type materials. The difficulty inherent in the production of p-type TCO is the strong localization of holes in binary metal oxides due to the electronegative character of oxygen ions.

In addition, the lack of understanding of the complex doping mechanism also hampers progress in the preparation of reproducible and stable materials. Among all p-type TCOs, NiO is representative, with its p-type conductivity without intentional doping and its forbidden broadband energy ranging from 3.6 to 4.0 ev [15]. Thin layers of NiO have been prepared by various deposition methods: chemical self-assembling, sol-gel, spray pyrolysis, magnetron sputtering and pulsed laser deposition [20-22]. Among these methods, the spray

pyrolysis is very simple and relatively cheap, extremely easy for the preparation of thin layers of different compositions. This process makes it possible to obtain well-adherent, transparent deposits of good crystalline quality.

In this article, we report the optical and electrical properties of thin layers of NiO, deposited on a glass substrate by pyrolysis spray by varying the experimental conditions. To study the effects of substrate temperature and spraying time on these properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS:

2.1 Sample preparation:

Figure 1. Shows the spray pyrolyse experimental setup used here to deposit NiO films onto glass substrates by spraying Nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate, 98%, ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution dissolved in doubly distilled water with concentration of 0.1 M. The distance between the substrates and the spray gun nozzle was fixed at 5 cm.

The spray solution was then sprayed in fine droplets onto glass substrates at temperature substrates of 350°C, 400°C, 450°C and 500°C in fixed time of 60 min. Then we changed the time of 30 min, 60 min, 90 min and 120 min with fixed temperature of 400°C.

Figure 1. Experimental layout used for spray pyrolysis of thin NiO films: 1, Electric gun; 2, nebulizer Omron; 3, plaque chauffante; 4, glass substrate; 5, Thermometre; 6, Nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate solution.

2.2 Sample characterization:

The crystallographic structure was studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique using (BRUKER - AXS type D8) equipped with X'Pert High Score under $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.540593 \text{ \AA}$) radiations for 2θ values in the range of 20-70°. The optical

transmittance $T(\lambda)$ and the reflectance $R(\lambda)$ of the films were measured by UV-vis-spectro-photometer (Shimadzu, Model 1800); the scanning measurements were ranged in 300-900 nm.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 Structural properties:

X-ray diffraction was used in order to understand the structure of the deposited NiO thin films on glass substrates brought to a molarity of 0.1 M at different temperatures heated substrates (350°C, 400°C, 450°C and 500°C) with fixed time of 1 hour (Figure 2-(a)) and at different times (30 min, 60 min, 90 min and 120 min) with fixed temperature of 400°C (Figure 2-(b)).

Figure 2-(a): the peak located at 37.4° is the (111) diffraction peak from cubic structure of NiO, the peak located at 43.55° is the (200) diffraction peak from cubic structure of NiO, the peak located at 43.55° is not very clear when the structure temperature is increased to 450°C and 500°C. Results show that the films are polycrystalline, consisting of NiO cubic phase with preferred orientation along (200) direction at the temperature higher than 400°C but is very clear when the temperature is 400°C, and (111) direction for temperature of 350°C, and an average reflection along (200) direction, the intensity of (200) peak is increased at the substrate temperature of 400°C.

Figure 2-(b): All samples exhibited peaks at (111) and (200), were indexed precisely to a cubic structure of NiO [15].

Figure 2. XRD patterns of NiO thin films deposited by spray pyrolysis with different substrate temperature (a) and different time (b) for a molarity of 0.1M.

The crystallite size of the NiO films was calculated, from the peaks with the highest intensity, using the Scherrer's equation [23]:

$$G = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \tag{1}$$

Where λ , θ and β are the wavelength, Bragg diffraction angle and full width at half maximum, respectively G is the grain size.

Table 1 Effects of the duration of pulverization on the crystallite size of NiO thin films:

Table 1 shows the variation of the crystallite size of NiO thin films developed by spray pyrolysis technique, with the deposition parameters, we noticed that the crystallite size increases with the duration of pulverization increase but is stabilizes at 90 Min and 120 min to 38,7 nm, for the films obtained with 0.1M concentration solution and 400°C temperature.

Table 2 shows the variation of the crystallite size of NiO thin films at various deposition temperatures, we noticed that the crystallite size of NiO thin films was affected by the increase of temperature, which it obtained a decrease.

Table 2 Effects of deposition temperature on the crystallite size of NiO thin films.

Table 1 Effects of the duration of pulverization on the crystallite size of NiO thin films:

$C_M=0.1 M, T=400^\circ C$								
Spray time t (min)	hkl	2θ(°)	B(°)	d_{hkl} (nm)	a (nm)	Taille de grain G (nm)	$d_{hkl moy}$ (nm)	G_{moy} (nm)
30 MIN	111	37.3785	0.2952	0.24	0.4157	28.40	0,3282	28.675
	200	43.4120	0.2952	0.4164	0.8328	28.95		
60 MIN	111	37,504	0.3936	0.2395	0.4148	20.1758	0,3273	30.2637
	200	43.5498	0.1968	0.4151	0.8302	40.3516		
90 MIN	111	37,3646	0.2460	0.24	0.4157	34,0257	0,32825	38.7587
	200	43.3979	0.1968	0.4165	0.8330	43,4917		
120 MIN	111	37.3914	0.1968	0,2402	0,416	42,597	0,3283	38,6708
	200	43.4110	0.2460	0,4164	0.8328	34,7447		

Table 2 Effects of deposition temperature on the crystallite size of NiO thin films:

$C_M=0.1 M, t=60 \text{ min}$								
Temperature substrates (°C)	hkl	2θ(°)	β(°)	d_{hkl} (nm)	a (nm)	Taille de grain G (nm)	$d_{hkl moy}$ (nm)	G_{moy} (nm)
350	111	37.3511	0.1476	0.2400	0.4165	59.7900	0.3281	37.1340
	200	43.4219	0.5904	0.4163	0.8326	14.4780		
400	111	37,5040	0.3936	0.2395	0.4148	20.1758	0,3273	30.2637
	200	43.5498	0.1968	0.4151	0.8302	40.3516		
450	111	36.2889	0.2952	0.2470	0.4278	28.3100	0,3318	25
	200	43.3691	0.3936	0.4167	0.8335	21.7143		
500	111	37.3523	0.1968	0,2404	0,4164	42,5945	0,3285	43
	200	43.3744	0.1968	0,4167	0.8334	43.4255		

Figure 3. Spectral variations of transmission of NiO thin films deposited by spray pyrolysis with different substrate temperature (a) and different time (b) for a molarity of 0.1M.

3.2 Optical properties:

Spectral transmittance shows in Figure 3 (a) and (b), Figure 3 (a): The transmission decreases when the spraying time increases except for 60 minutes the transmittance is greater than for 30 minutes then must be decreased for the other spraying times (90 min and 120 min). The films assemble a transmission between 80 % and 90 % for spraying duration of 60 minutes, and of the order of 70% up to 86 % for the other duration (30 min,90 min and 120 min).

Figure 3 (b):The transmission is increased with the increase in temperature from 350°C to 500°C; the films assemble a transmission between 70 % and 90 %.

In the optical method ,the band gap values are obtained from the following relation[24]:

$$\alpha h\nu = A(h\nu - E_g)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where A is a constant, α is the absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ is the photon energy and E_g is the band gap energy. The determination of the band gaps of the films have been calculated using Tauc's plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ and by extrapolating the linear

portion of the absorption edge to find the intercept with energy axis as shown in Figure 4 (a)et Figure 4 (b).

Figure 4 The dependence of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ on the incident photon energy $h\nu$ of NiO thin films deposited by spray pyrolysis with different substrate temperature (a) and different time (b) for a molarity of 0.1M.

The estimated optical gap energy increase from 3,57ev to 3,63ev in the substrate temperature from 350°C to 400°C ,then decrease to 3,4ev when the temperature increases from 400°C to 500°C (Figure 4 (a)),Indeed at high temperature the inter-atomic bonds are weakened, and when one has weaker bonds necessarily needs only a weak energy to break these bonds and obtain an electron in the conduction band. Temperature width of the gap decreases, the charge carriers are better able to aquirir superior thermal energy to the energy gap enabling them to cross the gap and move from the valence band to the conduction band.The gap energy decrease from 3,70ev to 3,5ev with an increase in the duration of pulverization (Figure 4 (b)). The crystalline mass of NiO has a band gap of approximately 4ev [15], which is close to the band gap values obtained for NiO films.

4. CONCLUSION:

In this work, NiO thin films were prepared by the spray pyrolysis technique under various experimental conditions. Thus, substrate temperature (from 350°C to 500°C) and time of pulverization (30 min to 120 min).

Several series of samples were prepared and their structural and optical properties studied in particular the highly orientated films obtained at a temperature of 400°C and molarity of 0.1 M,

All films have high transparency (70% to 90%). The average crystallite size of NiO is around nanometer (28.675 nm to 38, 6708 nm)

The optical band gap has been found to decrease from 3,70 eV to 3,53 eV with the increase in substrate temperature and increase from 3,36 eV to 3,6 eV with the increase in spray time. This suggestion is in good agreement with the values obtained for NiO thin films compared to pure NiO.

The spray deposit method (spray pyrolysis) is an important technique for producing thin films of NiO with good properties such as transparency, homogeneity, large area and low cost for many applications such as gas detection or the anti-reflective coating for solar cells ... etc.

However, additional studies are necessary to improve the electrical properties of the thin layers of NiO obtained for the application as TCO in thin-film solar cells.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Ginley, D.S., Bright, C.I., 2000. Transparent conducting oxides. Guest Editors, MRS Bull, 15–18.
- [2] C. G. Granqvist, Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells, 2007, 91, 1529–1598.
- [3] L. He and S. C. Tjong, Mater. Sci. Eng., R, 2016, 109, 1–101.
- [4] A. Mirzaei and G. Neri, Sens. Actuators, B, 2016, 237, 749–775.
- [5] H. Kawazoe, M. Yasukawa, H. Hyodo, M. Kurita, H. Yanagi, H. Hosono, Nature 389(1997) 939.
- [6] R. Nagarajan, A.D. Draeseke, A.W. Sleight, J. Tate, J. Appl. Phys. 89 (2001) 8022.
- [7] K. Ueda, T. Hase, H. Yanagi, H. Kawazoe, H. Hosono, J. Appl. Phys. 89 (2001) 1790.
- [8] H. Yanagi, T. Hase, S. Ibuki, K. Ueda, H. Hosono, Appl. Phys. Lett. 78 (2001) 1583.
- [9] N. Duan, A.W. Sleight, M.K. Jayaraj, J. Tate, Appl. Phys. Lett. 77 (2000) 1325.
- [10] B.J. Ingram, B.J. Harder, N.W. Hrabe, T.O. Mason, K. Poeppelmeier, Chem. Mater. 16(2004) 5623.
- [11] M. Snure, A. Tiwari, Appl. Phys. Lett. 91 (2007) 092123.
- [12] A. Kudo, H. Yanagi, H. Hosono, H. Kawazoe, Appl. Phys. Lett. 73 (1998) 220.
- [13] K. Ueda, S. Inoue, H. Hirose, H. Kawazoe, H. Hosono, Appl. Phys. Lett. 77 (2000) 2701.
- [14] H. Kamioka, H. Hidenori, H. Ohta, M. Hirano, K. Ueda, T. Kamiya, H. Hosono, Appl. Phys. Lett. 84 (2004) 879.
- [15] H. Sato, T. Minami, S. Takata, T. Yamada, Thin Solid Films 236 (1993) 27.
- [16] X.L. Guo, H. Tabata, T. Kawai, J. Cryst. Growth 223 (2001) 135.
- [17] K.K. Kim, H.S. Kim, D.K. Hwang, J.H. Lim, S.J. Parka, Appl. Phys. Lett. 83 (2003) 63.
- [18] M. Joseph, H. Tabata, H. Saeki, K. Ueda, T. Kawai, Phys. B 302 (2001) 140.
- [19] J.M. Bian, X.M. Li, X.D. Gao, W.D. Yu, L.D. Chen, Appl. Phys. Lett. 84 (2004) 541.
- [20] B. Sasi, K.G. Gopchandran, P.K. Manoj, P. Koshy, P.P. Rao, V.K. Vaidyan, Vacuum 68 (2003) 149.
- [21] H.L. Chen, Y.M. Lu, W.S. Hwang, Surf. Coat. Technol. 198 (2005) 138.
- [22] S.A. Makhlof, Thin Solid Films 516 (2008) 3112.
- [23] Francisco Tiago Leitão Muniz, Marcus A R Miranda, C. Morilla-Santos, José M. Sasaki. The Scherrer equation and the dynamical theory of X-ray diffraction, Acta Crystallographica Section A: Foundations and Advances 72(3) (May 2016).
- [24] J.M. Shah, Y.L. Li, T. Gessmann, E.F. Schubert, J. Appl. Phys. 94 (2003) 2627–2631.